

D2.2 – Guidelines for new communities integration

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Deliverable Abstract

This deliverable is intended to help new communities understand EPOS regulations regarding the establishment of a new TCS as well as to provide some practical recommendations for smoother integration of new communities into EPOS RI. This document should be read side-by-side with the Chapter 2.2 “*Establishment of a TCS*” of the “*EPOS ERIC Implementing Rules, Section 2*”. Present text provides an extensively commented version of these regulations. Practical recommendations provided inline with the official regulations regarding different stages of the establishment of a new TCS facilitate the understanding of ‘how EPOS works?’ and assist faster and smoother integration of new communities into the Research Infrastructure. Specifically, we prioritize the following tasks: (i) drafting the governance structure compatible to the EPOS model; (ii) distribution of roles and responsibilities in the community, including the role of the (interim) coordinator and various contact persons; (iii) starting regular meetings of the initiative group (a prototype of the future TCS Executive Board); (iv) fair assessment of community assets as potential services including aspects of their financial sustainability and technical readiness level for the seamless integration into the EPOS Platform; (v) participation to the regular ICS-TCS meetings to learn technical aspects of service provision within the EPOS Delivery Framework; (vi) selection of 1-2 pilot services and starting their practical integration into EPOS Delivery Framework.

In the Appendix we present a draft template of a TCS consortium agreement.

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TERMINOLOGY

Acronym	Definition
DDSS	Data, Data products, Software and Services
ECO	Executive Coordination Office
ICS	Integrated Core Services
RI	Research Infrastructure
SCC	Service Coordination Committee
TCS	Thematic Core Services

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1 Executive summary

Aim of the Deliverable:

This document is intended to help new communities understand EPOS regulations regarding the establishment of a new TCS as well as to provide some practical recommendations for smoother integration of new communities into EPOS RI.

How to read this document:

This document should be read side-by-side with the Chapter 2.2 “*Establishment of a TCS*” of the “*EPOS ERIC Implementing Rules, Section 2*”.

The process of establishment of a new EPOS Thematic Core Service (TCS) is regulated by Chapter 2.2 “*Establishment of a TCS*” of one of the EPOS main constitutive documents – “*EPOS ERIC Implementing Rules, Section 2*”. Current Deliverable provides an extensively commented version of these regulations. Comments in the form of guidelines are intended to explain the background of the specific regulations and to provide recommendations for their practical implementations. They are largely based on the experience of the TCS Tsunami – a new EPOS thematic community, which officially joined EPOS RI in February 2024 after a long period of preparatory work including the Candidate TCS phase.

The Deliverable first introduces considerations regarding the benefits of a community to be a part of the EPOS family. Practical recommendations provided in line with the official regulations regarding different stages of the establishment of a new TCS facilitate the understanding of “how EPOS works?” and assist faster and smoother integration of new communities into the Research Infrastructure. Specifically, we prioritize following tasks: (i) drafting the governance structure compatible to the EPOS model; (ii) distribution of roles and responsibilities in the community, including the role of the (interim) coordinator and various contact persons; (iii) starting regular meetings of the initiative group (a prototype of the future TCS Executive Board); (iv) fair assessment of community assets as potential services including aspects of their financial sustainability and technical readiness level for the seamless integration into the EPOS Platform; (v) participation to the regular ICS-TCS meetings to learn technical aspects of service provision within the EPOS Delivery Framework; (vi) selection of 1-2 pilot services and starting their practical integration into EPOS Delivery Framework. In the Appendix we present a draft template of TCS consortium agreement.

2 Introduction

The European Plate Observing System (EPOS) is the sole distributed pan-European Research Infrastructure (RI) for solid Earth Science, enabling open access to high-quality, multidisciplinary assets: data, data products, software and services – ‘DDSS elements’ in EPOS-terminology. Being conceptually initiated in 1997 and evolving through various construction phases – conceptual, preparatory, implementation, and pilot operation phase – EPOS RI has started its full operational phase in 2023. Essentially EPOS RI develops and provides a federated research platform for coordinated access to harmonized and quality-controlled DDSS elements from diverse Earth science disciplines. In this way EPOS implements its main mission: fosters worldwide interoperability in Earth sciences and provides services to a broad community of users.

From a researcher’s point of view, EPOS RI is organized by thematic professional communities, also called as Thematic Core Services (TCS), see Figure 1.

Figure 1: Architecture of EPOS RI. Main component – EPOS Delivery Framework – consists of the union of solid Earth communities (left-hand side) also called Thematic Core Services and the platform for harmonized and quality-controlled data and service provision called Integrated Core Services (ICS) (right hand side)

At time of writing, as of July 2025, there are ten (10) Thematic Core Services (or professional Communities) officially contributing to EPOS RI:

- Seismology;
- Near-fault Observatories;
- GNSS Data and Products;
- Volcano Observations;
- Satellite Data;

- Geomagnetic Observations;
- Anthropogenic Hazards;
- Geological Information and Modeling;
- Multi-scale Laboratories;
- Tsunami.

Nine of these, except TCS Tsunami, were established at the earlier stages of EPOS construction being intrinsically and tightly integrated parts of the RI since many years, whereas Tsunami community has been the first professional community joining EPOS RI after its official establishment.

This Deliverable is to a large extent based on the experience gained by the Tsunami community on their way from getting the first idea to establish EPOS TCS Tsunami (fall of 2018) to finally obtaining the status of a full TCS in February 2024.

The last revision of one of the EPOS main constitutive documents – *EPOS ERIC Implementing Rules, Section 2* – explicitly regulates the process of establishment of a new EPOS Thematic Core Service (TCS) in Chapter 2.2 called “Establishment of a TCS”. This process includes three stages: (i) preliminary, preparatory phase; (ii) Candidate TCS phase and (iii) formal establishment of a TCS. In the chapters below, we will address these stages in detail by browsing through the *Implementing Rules, Section 2, Ch. 2.2* and providing extensive comments to the individual steps. But first, we will provide argumentation – why a professional community could be interested in joining EPOS RI? Which could be potential benefits for a community to become a part of the EPOS family?

One of the main goals, if not the main, of a new community on their way to EPOS is the self-organisation of the community justified by partner’s readiness to sign TCS Consortium Agreement. EPOS management treats TCSs as independent and sovereign consortia which are free in organizing themselves. This is one reason why there is no official template for the EPOS TCS Consortium Agreement. On another hand, governance structure and operational mode of a TCS consortium should be compliant with the EPOS structure and functionality. As the Tsunami Community started its first integration steps, we were looking for a prototype text for our future Consortium Agreement. Looking back at that period, we decided to convert our present TCS Consortium Agreement into a generic draft template and add it to the Appendix of this Deliverable. This draft may be useful as a reference text for a new community starting to think about their possible governance structure and other formalities of a TCS daily life.

3 Part I: Value for a Community to become EPOS TCS

As mentioned above, EPOS society is organized by discipline-specific research communities – Thematic Core Services (Figure 1). Thematic Core Services (TCS), in turn, are organized as consortia whose members are national research institutions. The same research institution may be a member of several EPOS TCS consortia, depending on the involvement of various research units and teams. For example, INGV (Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia) has signed consortium agreements with a number of TCSs including TCS Seismology, Tsunami, Volcano Observations, etc. Thus, while being formally composed of research institutions, TCSs essentially represent communities of individual researchers and research groups from various European countries. This fact explains the dominant “community spirit” of TCSs, where a research community, not institutions, becomes a driver of a TCS.

This “community-centered” vision should be always kept in mind whenever addressing already existing or newly planned major EPOS RI elements that are Thematic Core Services (TCS). Correspondingly, the idea to establish a new EPOS TCS usually arises within the scope of a specific professional pan-European research community. A seed for such an idea could be, for example, positive feedback regarding the benefits of being a part of the EPOS family received from institutional colleagues from existing TCS or colleagues from the European partnership.

There are numerous benefits for a research community to become EPOS TCS. Despite being community-specific, we can formulate main benefits of a generic, cross-TCS nature.

- First of all, TCS can be treated as a Community integration platform.

Indeed, individual researchers from different institutions are used to cooperate with each other within the scope of joint international projects, in particular, within European Commission funded collaborative projects. These projects are, however, limited in time and by topic. EPOS TCS, in contrast, provides a platform to get together on a more permanent basis.

- Communities will strongly benefit from being organized in a formal way.

TCS will build a democratic governance structure with distribution of roles and responsibilities, seeking for consensus in prioritizing short- and long-term development goals.

- Joint activity shall motivate synergy and interoperability (e.g., building and development of international community standards for data and models).
- The EPOS mission of harmonized service provision, supported by regular exchange of experience and help from the professional EPOS IT team, shall motivate individual researchers to bring their assets – datasets, software, applications, etc. – to end-users in a best professional way.
- Researchers and institutions will benefit from rich networking.

For example, from closer participation to joint fundraising programs (e.g., EC-projects).

- Last but not the least: annual EPOS ERIC grant for TCSs, while being limited by volume, shall help to keep TCS together by supporting community life and contribution to the common EPOS development goals.

Summarizing, organizing research communities into EPOS TCS strengthens communities by developing “community spirit”, providing a sustainable platform for idea interaction and joint activities, and harmonizing efforts towards interoperable joint and individual scientific products.

4 Part II: Preliminary work

The process of establishment of a new EPOS Thematic Core Service (TCS) is being regulated by Chapter 2.2 “Establishment of a TCS” of one of the EPOS main constitutive documents – *EPOS ERIC Implementing Rules, Section 2*.

From now on we will extensively cite this document and comment on sections aimed at guiding New Communities through the process of construction and establishment of a new TCS. Text in *italic* will be citations from the EPOS document followed by our comments.

We start with Chapter 2.2, section 2.2.1 “General requirements” which describes the first practical action – application to become a Candidate TCS.

“The process to become a TCS starts with the application to become a Candidate TCS. The application shall be addressed to the EPOS ERIC Executive Director and be supported by at least three organizations from a thematic community.” – Communities willing to join EPOS RI won’t be granted the “full TCS” status automatically. Instead, new communities will be requested to perform preparatory work, and for that they will be granted a status of ‘Candidate TCS’ for a maximum of 3 years. At the end of the Candidate phase, the community should be 100% ready to be integrated into the EPOS RI.

However, as it can be seen from section 2.2.1, requesting the status of a Candidate TCS also needs some preliminary work to be done by the community. In short – a new community (or the core members of the future community) should already *agree on the canvas* of their future TCS. And only after reaching to a consensus, to a commonly shared answers to the following questions:

- who are we? what defines (the boundaries of) our community?
- why do we want to be in EPOS?
- are we ready to build a sustainable consortium with a time perspective of 10 years?
- to share the roles and to accept responsibilities?
- which could be our positioning in EPOS? synergy with other TCSs?
- can we ensure financial and technical sustainability of our proposed services for at least 5 years?

should new community start with the application to become a candidate TCS.

As cited above, the application should be supported by *at least three* organizations from a thematic community. This is important – involvement of a number of partner institutions shall demonstrate the earnestness but also maturity of the community plans. Also organizationally probably more complicated, we nevertheless recommend to include as much as possible potential partners already at this stage. Community building is, first of all, a matter of “community spirit”. Especially when it comes to novel mobilizing initiatives such as the creation of a new EPOS TCS. Inviting as much as possible partners “on board” will positively work for the community spirit. It is also wise from the practical point of view to distribute numerous roles, assigned within TCS, among more partners to balance their in-kind contributions. Also earlier involvement of more partners shall help to timely assess and to compile/prepare (also from the technical point of view)

future TCS service portfolio – a list of DDSS elements to be distributed by TCS within the scope of EPOS Delivery Framework.

“The proposed thematic community shall offer pan-European services that are relevant for but not yet available through EPOS.” – Here, under the word “services” we understand provision of various research assets/products, in EPOS terminology called ‘DDSS-elements’ where DDSS stands for: Data, Data products, Software and Services. Historically, EPOS Data Portal was constructed to distribute data and data products via the OGC (Open Geospatial Consortium) compliant web-services WMS (Web Map Service) and WFS (Web Feature Service). However, currently, EPOS Delivery Framework becomes more generic and progressively includes also distribution of software (SaaS – Software as a Service) and workflows (WaaS – Workflow as a Service), access provision to (data-)processing and advanced visualization tools, Jupyter notebooks and (web-)applications. In the near future EPOS also plans to open access to experimental and lab facilities via the mechanism of trans-national access (TA).

Services to be proposed by a new community should be relevant to the EPOS profile, i.e. belong to the field of the solid Earth, and be unique at the platform.

Further on, Section 2.2.1 specifies items to be included into the application to become a Candidate TCS.

“The application shall include:

- *the list of organizations supporting the application, their role and engagement within the thematic community;”* – See comment regarding the founding organizations (at least three) at the previous page.
- *“the contact person for each participating organization;”* – An individual, who will represent the organization - future TCS consortium member - in the process of TCS construction on behalf of this organization. Note, while signing TCS consortium agreement, organizations will nominate their representatives to the Consortium Board – perspective to keep in mind when designating a contact person at present stage.
- *“the contact details of the (interim) Coordinator that will represent the thematic community within EPOS during the preparatory phase (Section 2.2.3 of this document);”* – TCS community in EPOS is a self-standing consortium of institutional partners. The consortium follows EPOS mission and goals but is independent in its governance and decisions. EPOS management in the form of ECO (Executive Coordination Office) liaises with TCS consortium through the so-called ‘TCS Coordinator’ – a representative from the organization that is being nominated by the consortium to represent it within EPOS RI for administrative and financial issues. Specifically, EPOS ERIC and TCS Coordinator sign bilateral Multi-Year Collaboration Agreement (MYCA) for TCS Governance and Service Provision for a time period of 5 years. Thus, by fact, TCS Coordinator plays as an interface, a front-end, between the TCS consortium and EPOS ERIC in what concerns legal, administrative and financial issues. To give one example: according to the MYCA agreement, EPOS ERIC transfers TCS Coordinator the annual grant to support TCS governance and service provision. TCS Coordinator, in turn, distributes this grant to TCS

partners according to the earlier decisions on funding priorities made by the consortium itself (according to the annual Work Plan). The coordinator then observes the implementation of the Work Plan and, after the end of the funding period, collects scientific, administrative and financial reports from the beneficiaries, produces TCS summary reports and conveys them to EPOS ECO. Thus, the role of (interim) TCS Coordinator is a special role which presumes a large amount of coordination work within a relatively long period (MYCA agreement is valid for 5 years) – new communities should be aware of that when proposing their future Coordinator. Of course, the TCS Coordinator shall not be the only partner representing all the aspects of TCS activities in EPOS. EPOS internal life assumes working in different committees and working groups, along various directions: IT issues, data policy, ethical issues, communication and outreach, and so on. That is why it will be crucially important to distribute these functions and roles with the new community among various partners. Such taking-over responsibilities shall also strengthen community spirit and sustainability. For a typical roles and functions distribution model, see e.g. the draft template of the TCS Consortium Agreement, Section 7.3 in the Appendix.

- “the list of initial pan-European data, data products, software, and services (DDSS) proposed for integration in EPOS and an explanation of how these DDSS will contribute to achieving the EPOS mission;”* – Mission of the EPOS as European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) is “to provide sustainable, long-term, and open access to solid Earth science data and services integrating diverse European Research Infrastructures under a federated framework” (cited after ESFRI Research Infrastructures Portfolio: <https://ri-portfolio.esfri.eu/ri-portfolio/portfolio-editions/2024-first-edition/catalogue/epos-eric/>).

The key words here are “sustainable, long-term, and open” access to data, data products, software and services. By proposing a list of future DDSS elements, the new community should especially pay attention to the aspect of *sustainable long-term* service provision. Recall that the Multi-Year Collaboration Agreement (MYCA) for TCS service provision will be signed for 5 years. That sets the minimal time horizon for each service in the list to be functional and 100% accessible in 24/7 mode. Similar to the recommendation to involve the maximum number of the TCS potential partners from the very beginning of TCS construction, we also recommend not to delay the integration of services into the EPOS Delivery Framework. The list of DDSS elements “proposed for integration” should not necessarily contain only assets which are technically ready to be integrated. Some of the listed assets may stay on the “integration roadmap”, and TCS may develop its own strategy on service integration. But we believe that it is important – for both the new community and EPOS – to set up a clear vision and feasible strategic plan regarding (near-)future community contribution to EPOS. For the new community that will set a roadmap, for the EPOS RI will help to assess the new community positioning and role inside the infrastructure.
- “an indication of the financial sustainability of the proposed services, including an initial estimate of the costs and funds (including in-kind) for operating each service; for that purpose, the EPOS ERIC Executive Director will provide indications on the EPOS cost and*

funding model;” - EPOS does not develop new services. EPOS provides a platform for harmonized distribution of the already existing services developed and supported by partner organisations. According to the EPOS policy, EPOS grants cannot be used for service development or essential service provision. This grant can be instead used to integrate the already existing service into the EPOS Delivery Framework. Such an integration may, of course, require service modification or upgrade to the EPOS community standards. EPOS grant can also cover service provision in part that is necessary for service to be accessible via the EPOS platform. That all means that TCS services, in their essentials, should not be dependent on EPOS funding and must be sustainably operated by TCS partners; in a way in-kind in relation to EPOS. To demonstrate financial sustainability of services, each TCS should compile and periodically update a so-called ‘cost-book’ where service costs including costs of service provision are presented together with their funding models. The format of the cost-book will be provided by ECO. On request, ECO also assists in the compilation of the cost-book.

- *“if applicable, an overview of potential collaborations with other existing TCS;”* – Presently EPOS RI hosts 10 thematic communities acting in different fields of solid Earth science (see Introduction). TCSs provide their community-specific services but EPOS is always looking for a potential synergy between the communities to explore possibilities of new, cross-domain services and also to promote multi-disciplinary usage of the EPOS platform. It is exactly that usage which can demonstrate the added value of EPOS philosophy: unified access to the vast family of harmonized multi-disciplinary services. That is why the new community should try to position itself within the EPOS ecosystem and to assess potential synergies with other TCSs.
- *“if applicable, a plan for expanding the number of stakeholders of the thematic community;”*
- *“an initial proposal for the governance model compatible with the role and responsibilities of TCS as established in Section 2.1 of this document;”* – There will be enough time for a new community to develop and to agree on the new TCS Consortium Agreement – a set of regulations defining consortium governance model and modality of work. Specifically, that should be the main task of the Candidate phase. However, already in the application to become Candidate TCS, EPOS management wants to see the draft of the new TCS governance model. That is to be ensured that the new community understands and shares the philosophy and basic principles of EPOS. In the Appendix, draft template for the TCS Consortium Agreement, we present a sample governance model in Section 7 of the document.
- *“acknowledgment of the EPOS Policies (Section 6 of this document) and willingness to adopt them by the thematic community.”* – Being a part of the EPOS family also means sharing of community values: be it data-, citation-, or licensing policy, or ethical aspects.

To summarize, new communities should not underestimate the significance of the preparatory work which, on one hand, is necessary to prepare a formal application to become a Candidate TCS. On another hand, by doing this work, community already starts to plan its future, especially for

what concerns governance model, distribution of roles and responsibilities inside the community, fair assessment of the available community assets which will be distributed on behalf of the whole community, as well as degree of their (assets) maturity for integration into the EPOS Delivery Framework.

5 Part III: Candidate phase

After the application to become a Candidate TCS will be sent to the EPOS ERIC Executive Director, according to the EPOS Implementing Rules, section 2.2.2 *“Evaluation of the application”*:

“The Executive Director shall assess the application, in consultation with the Service Coordination Committee, the Executive Committee and the Scientific Board and report back to the (interim) Coordinator within three months. If positively assessed, the matter will be brought to the General Assembly for a decision on accepting the thematic community for a candidate phase period of up to three years, during which it shall be required to respond to the requirements of an established EPOS TCS.” – Service Coordination Committee (SCC) has a special role in EPOS RI. SCC is composed of representatives of all the EPOS Thematic Communities and, by fact, defines priorities in EPOS development from the researcher’s point of view. According to the EPOS ERIC Statutes, Article 13, paragraph 4: *“The Executive Director shall consult the Service Coordination Committee for all general matters including drawing up proposals for the General Assembly in establishing and modifying annual working plans to ensure consistence, coherence and stability of the operation of the research infrastructure.”* The interim Coordinator of the new community will be invited to regular meetings of the SCC to introduce the new community and to convince SCC about the value of this community for EPOS. Members of the SCC vote for the proposal and then, in case of the positive outcome, the EPOS Executive Director brings the application to the consideration at the General Assembly (meetings of the General Assembly take place twice a year, usually in May and December). The General Assembly is the governing body of EPOS ERIC and is composed of representatives of the member states (European countries) and observers of EPOS ERIC (EPOS ERIC Statutes, Article 10, paragraph 1).

In case of a positive decision of the General Assembly, the new community obtains the status of a Candidate TCS for a time period of up to three years. During this period, the community shall *“respond to the requirements of an established EPOS TCS”*. These requirements are clearly listed in Chapter 2.1 *“Roles and Responsibilities”* of the governing document *“EPOS ERIC Implementing Rules, Section 2”*. Despite their application to the already established (“full-sized”) Thematic Communities, we believe it is worth citing these requirements in the present *“Guidelines for New Communities”* to give new communities a clear perspective of what they have to respond to at the end of their Candidate phase.

Namely, established *“TCS shall:*

- *Ensure access to solid Earth science data, data products, software and services of their thematic domain under the EPOS Delivery Framework.*
- *Identify the TCS representative in the Service Coordination Committee.*
- *Have a TCS Consortium Agreement (CA) in force, outlining the mission of the TCS together with the organizational, managerial and financial guidelines to be followed by the TCS Consortium. The CA may include relevant annexes as required. As a minimum, the TCS CA shall:*

- *include at least three TCS Consortium members as signatories, and maintain an up-to-date list of Consortium members (as an annex);*
- *set out the purpose of the CA;*
- *establish the procedures for adding, withdrawing or removing TCS Consortium members;*
- *establish when the CA enters into force, as well as its duration and termination;*
- *describe the TCS governance structure, including the description of boards and committees and their main operational procedures;*
- *identify the ultimate decision-making body of the TCS and regulate the appointment of its members and election of the Chair;*
- *establish the procedures for the provision of services under the EPOS Delivery Framework;*
- *maintain a list of TCS services and their service providers (as annex);*
- *specify the liabilities of the TCS Consortium members;*
- *specify the financial provisions regarding the participation of the TCS Consortium members in the consortium;*
- *require its signatories to comply with the EPOS Policies (as in Chapter 6 of this document), and establish provisions regarding intellectual property rights, ownership and dissemination of data and results, as well as on information disclosure;*
 - *specify the legal framework under which the CA operates.*
- *Inform the EPOS ERIC Executive Director of any change in the Consortium Agreement, including the addition, withdrawal, or removal of TCS Consortium members.*
- *Enter into Collaboration Agreements which will set out the annual work plans and budgets agreed by the TCS Consortium members and with EPOS ERIC.*
- *Designate the TCS Consortium member/s in charge of signing Collaboration Agreements with EPOS ERIC.*
- *Establish and periodically update a cost-book to monitor the TCS sustainability.*
- *Facilitate TCS contacts to EPOS ERIC as requested by the Executive Coordination Office.*
- *Ensure the circulation of EPOS ERIC's communications to the TCS Consortium members.*
- *Ensure that the management plans for data, product and service provision are kept up to date and further developed as required.*
- *Ensure and maintain the connection with the thematic community and its integration in EPOS.*
- *Use the EPOS brand according to the EPOS Communication Plan."*

As mentioned above, these are requirements to the already established "full-size" TCSs. A Candidate TCS should use its Candidate phase to become 100% compatible to these requirements. To achieve this task, EPOS proposes a mechanism described in Section 2.2.3 "Candidate phase" of the *Implementing Rules, Section 2*.

"During the candidate phase the thematic community shall:

- *“have the status of Candidate TCS and be allowed to use the EPOS brand;”* – No comment needed here.
- *“be invited to participate in the Service Coordination Committee, as an observer;”* – Above we explained the role of the Service Coordination Committee (SCC) as EPOS main consulting and science policy developing body. SCC is composed of representatives of all existing TCSs. The new community delegates its representative to the SCC in the observer status, i.e., this representative takes part in all the meetings (online and in-person) of the SCC, takes part in SCC discussion but has no voting rights. The candidate TCS is free to nominate any of its members – nominations shall be approved by the EPOS Executive Director – but we recommend nominating a TCS Coordinator due to the practical reasons. TCS Coordinator of a new Candidate TCS has to be rapidly integrated into the daily EPOS life and obtain a comprehensive view on everything around – participating in the regular SCC meetings is the best way to achieve this integration. SCC also allows TCS representatives to have their “proxies”; if not as direct representative, TCS Coordinator could be alternatively nominated as a proxy.
- *“be granted access to the EPOS Intranet with a dedicated repository area;”* – Not only a repository area, EPOS Intranet allows creation of various TCS mailing lists. For example, it makes sense to create mailing lists for TCS governing bodies and groups: for Consortium Board members, members of the Executive Board list, Service Provision group, etc.
- *“become eligible for EPOS ERIC funds, depending on the General Assembly decision, to support the building of the thematic community during the candidate phase;”* – EPOS management and SCC may propose a General Assembly to approve a dedicated budget to support “new communities” (around €100K per year). If this happens to be the case, the Candidate TCS can use this budget for TCS building, for example, to organize meetings of future Consortium partners, hackathons of the working group preparing Consortium Agreement. It is also worthwhile to financially motivate and support integration of the first selected community services (DDSS elements) into the EPOS Delivery Framework.
- *“ensure the necessary resources in order to gradually achieve the required technical harmonization and integration;”* – As explained above in Chapter 4 of this document, EPOS financial model assumes community services to be provided principally “in-kind” by partner organizations. EPOS financial support may cover only integration of the already existing services into the EPOS Delivery Framework and, to some extent, extra-costs of service provision arising due to the service accessibility through the EPOS portal. Current item stresses again the requirement to ensure sustainable and long-term (at least five years) service provision on principally own costs.
- *“liaise with the EPOS ERIC Communication Unit to coordinate communication and dissemination of the proposed thematic community in line with the EPOS Communication Plan;”* - EPOS, as a union of various thematic communities, implements a series of common tasks on a daily basis. These tasks contribute to the daily life of the organisation and involve representatives from all TCSs. Communication and outreach activity is one of these tasks. This activity is coordinated by the EPOS Communication Unit. Each TCS including Candidate TCS nominates 1-2 representatives as their contacts on communication and

outreach. TCS contacts stay connected with the EPOS Communication Unit and take active part in EPOS communication and dissemination actions for in- and outside.

- *“participate in the ICS-TCS System workshops;”* – The core of the EPOS Delivery Framework is EPOS Data Portal where most of the services are distributed. A special unit in EPOS – IT team lead by EPOS IT Officer – is in charge of all the technical and IT-items of the EPOS digital infrastructure. The IT team provides a framework for the harmonized service provision called Integrated Core Services (ICS). For this framework to be convenient for both service providers and external users, the ICS team seeks for a permanent feedback from the TCSs. TCSs, in turn, seek for the consultations and support from the ICS team while integrating their services into the EPOS Platform. Service providers may additionally request new IT-features enabling better presentation of their services. All these tasks require a constant dialogue between TCSs and EPOS IT team. To facilitate this dialogue and to set it on a permanent basis, EPOS IT proposed a mechanism of regular “ICS-TCS workshops”. These workshops take part four times a year. During workshops, which usually last for 3-5 days, participants are invited to propose mini-projects – “pitches”. Every pitch is concentrated on one single specific goal and has to be accomplished within one inter-workshop period (in three months). Pitch results are to be reported at the next regular workshop.

For new communities, pitches are an effective mechanism to start integration of their services into EPOS. We recommend selecting 1-2 services with the highest technical readiness level and propose pitches for their practical integration. If accepted, EPOS ICS management will nominate their colleagues with corresponding competence to facilitate new service integration. Since the dialogue between ICS and TCS is an ongoing process, Candidate TCS should nominate their contacts on “IT-issues” and on “service provision”. It is expected that these contacts will take over coordination of the liaison between TCS and ICS team and will be acting as an interface between TCS members and EPOS IT.

- *actively work towards achieving the status of EPOS TCS as defined in Section 2.1 of this document;*
- *provide the Executive Coordination Office with a yearly report on the progress achieved by the proposed thematic community for its integration in EPOS.* – A task for the TCS Coordinator.

At the end of the Candidate phase, the new community should (i) be internally organized and ready to sign their own Consortium Agreement and (ii) be able to start their service provision within EPOS Platform.

6 Part IV: Final preparations

The final stage of becoming a new TCS is comprehensively described in the final Section 2.2.4 “Request to become an EPOS TCS” of the Chapter 2.2 “Establishment of a TCS”, document EPOS ERIC Implementing Rules, Section 2.

“Within the end of three years of the candidate phase, the Candidate TCS wishing to become an EPOS TCS, shall submit to the Executive Director the following documents as part of the request:

- *a request letter signed by the (interim) Coordinator explaining how the TCS will comply with the requirements in Section 2.1;*
- *“the draft TCS Consortium Agreement;”* – Not yet signed. The community should wait for the final positive decision of the General Assembly and only after that circulate Consortium Agreement for signing by partner institutions.
- *“a letter signed by each member of the intended TCS Consortium (at least three TCS Consortium members as defined in Section 2.1 of this document).”* – Mentioned here are Letters of Commitment (LoC) to sign the new TCS Consortium Agreement.

“Within six months, the Executive Director, following consultation with the Service Coordination Committee and Executive Committee, will bring the matter for decision to the General Assembly. The recognition of the new TCS will be effective after the approval of the General Assembly and once the TCS Consortium Agreement is in force.” – TCS Coordinator, after reporting to the Service Coordination Committee, will be likely invited to report the outcomes of the Candidate phase and the current state-of-the-art of the TCS life and service provision also directly to the General Assembly. Coordinator should be prepared to address questions regarding financial aspects and sustainability of new TCS service provision, i.e. be fit for the critical discussion regarding the TCS cost-book.

Note, new TCS will be officially established (i) after the positive decision of the General Assembly, (ii) on the day once Consortium Agreement comes into force – usually when signed by at least three partners.

“If, within the end of three years of the candidate phase, the Candidate TCS will not request to become an EPOS TCS, the provisions outlined in Section 2.2.3 will cease to apply.” – Three years is a long term but there are also many tasks to be accomplished during this period, both by organizing partners into an effectively operating Consortium, as well as by technical integration of pilot services into the EPOS Delivery Framework. In particular, new communities should not underestimate time that may become necessary for institutional legal offices to iterate on and to approve the new consortium agreement.

7 Conclusions

Chapter 2.2 “*Establishment of a TCS*” of one of the EPOS main constitutive documents – *EPOS ERIC Implementing Rules, Section 2* – in a clear and concise way describes steps and requirements of the process of establishment of a new EPOS Thematic Core Service (TCS). Current Deliverable is intended to be read side-by-side with the Chapter 2.2 and essentially provides an extensively commented version of these regulations. Comments in the form of recommendations and guidelines are largely based on the experience of the TCS Tsunami – a new EPOS thematic community, which officially joined EPOS RI in February 2024 after a period of preparatory work including the Candidate TCS phase.

Despite the (seemingly) long period – 3 years – granted to new communities for the so-called Candidate phase, during which a community should become ready to meet EPOS requirements to Thematic Communities, we urge new communities not to relax but instead to make a fast start. Specifically, we propose to put a special attention, to prioritize the following tasks:

- drafting the governance structure compatible to the EPOS model;
- agreeing on distribution of roles and responsibilities in the community, including the role of the (interim) coordinator and various contact persons;
- starting regular meetings of the initiative group (a prototype of the future TCS Executive Board);
- fair assessment of community assets as potential services including aspects of their financial sustainability and technical readiness level for the seamless integration into the EPOS Platform;
- participation to the regular ICS-TCS meetings to learn technical aspects of service provision within the EPOS Delivery Framework;
- prioritization of 1-2 pilot services and starting their practical integration into EPOS Delivery Framework.

The above is a non-exhaustive list of the conceptual and practical tasks that should not be postponed but started from the very beginning, even before the community acquires the official status of Candidate TCS.

We hope the current document can be useful for new thematic communities that are considering the opportunity or already have decided to join the EPOS family.

Appendix

EPOS TCS XXX CONSORTIUM AGREEMENT

BETWEEN:

1. partner-1 Name (Abbreviation)
Address
PIC:
2. partner-2 Name (Abbreviation)
Address
PIC:

.....

.....

hereinafter jointly or individually referred to as “Parties” or “Party”,

WHEREAS:

The Parties wish to define their rights and obligations as part of the EPOS Thematic Core Service (TCS) XXX which is providing data and services to the EPOS Research Infrastructure.

IT IS THEREFORE HEREBY AGREED AS FOLLOWS:

.1 SECTION: DEFINITIONS

.1.1 DEFINITIONS

Words beginning with a capital letter shall have the specific meaning defined in this Consortium Agreement.

.1.2 ADDITIONAL DEFINITIONS

“*Background*”: is here defined as any data, data products, software, know-how or information – whatever its form or nature (tangible or intangible) – including any rights such as intellectual property rights that: (a) is held by the beneficiary before they acceded to the Agreement, and (b) is needed in the TCS activities.

“*Consortium Body*”: Consortium Body means any management body described in the Governance Structure section of this Consortium Agreement.

“*Collaboration Agreement*”: EPOS ERIC sets out Collaboration Agreements to formalise the activities of the TCS within the EPOS Delivery Framework. Envisaged are the following types of Collaboration Agreements: (i) for TCS Governance and Coordination; (ii) for TCS Data and Service Provision; (iii) for TCS Coordination of Transnational Access. The three Collaboration Agreements (i, ii, iii) can be combined into one single agreement with one signatory. Signed between EPOS ERIC and designated Member(s) of the Consortium.

“Coordinator” or “TCS Coordinator”: Member of the Consortium signing the *Collaboration Agreement for TCS Governance and Coordination* with EPOS ERIC. Its representing person automatically becomes chairperson of the Executive Board.

“DDSS”: acronym for “Data, Data Products, Software and Services”.

“DDSS Supplier”: Institution delivering DDSS through different means.

“EPOS ERIC”: European Plate Observing System European Research Infrastructure Consortium.

“Force majeure”: means any situation or event that:

- prevents either party from fulfilling their obligations under the Consortium Agreement,
- was unforeseeable, exceptional situation and beyond the parties’ control,
- was not due to error or negligence on their part (or on the part of third parties involved in the situation or event), and
- proves to be inevitable in spite of exercising all due diligence.

“Results”: means any (tangible or intangible) output of the activities within the Work Plan such as data, data products, software, knowledge or information — whatever its form or nature – as well as any rights attached to it, including intellectual property rights.

“TCS”: Thematic Core Services is a transnational governance framework enabling community-specific integration and coordination with the ultimate goal of provision of DDSS-elements within the EPOS Delivery Framework. ‘TCS XXX’ is formed by current Consortium.

“TA”: Trans National Access is physical or remote access to installations/infrastructures for selected users.

“VA”: Virtual Access is remote access to installations/infrastructures open to all users (registration may be required).

“Work Plan”: means the tasks and related costs agreed between the Consortium and EPOS ERIC for each calendar year for the purpose of achieving the objectives of common interest as outlined in the Collaboration Agreement(s).

.2 SECTION: PURPOSE

The purpose of this Consortium Agreement is to specify organisational, managerial and financial guidelines to be followed by the Consortium forming EPOS TCS XXX.

The mission of TCS XXX is to provide, through the EPOS Delivery Framework, products and services defined in following categories:

- category 1 description;
- category 2 description
-

Products and services, in EPOS notation ‘DDSS elements’ – Data, Data products, Software and Services – will be provided through the official EPOS Integrated Core Services (ICS-C) Data Portal (<https://www.ics-c.epos-eu.org/>), through the TCS XXX Community Portal ([link to XXX community portal\(s\)](#)), or in case of Trans National Accesses directly through the participating Partners.

.3 SECTION: ACCESSION OF A NEW PARTY, WITHDRAWAL OR REMOVAL OF A PARTY

.3.1 ACCESSION OF NEW ENTITIES

Entities wishing to join the EPOS TCS **XXX** Consortium, have to first complete a document in which they describe the proposed services and/or activities. This information will be used by the Consortium Board (sect. 7.2) to decide by a unanimous decision if the entity will become a new Party of the EPOS TCS **XXX** Consortium.

Such accession shall have effect from the date agreed between the new Party and the Consortium Board as identified in the accession document. The activities and resources of the new Party will be described in the accession document.

.3.2 WITHDRAWAL OF REMOVAL OF A PARTY

Any Party may withdraw from the Consortium upon request, provided that three (3) months prior notice is given to the Consortium Board. The withdrawing Party undertakes to complete its commitment taken up in the current Work Plan. The Terms of withdrawal shall be fixed by a specific agreement under provisions set out in the section 7.2.2.

In case a breach by a Party of its obligations under this Consortium Agreement is identified, the Consortium Board will give written notice to such Party requiring that such breach be remedied within 30 calendar days. If such breach is substantial and is not remedied within that period or is not capable of remedy, the Consortium Board may decide to declare the Party to be a defaulting Party and to decide on the consequences thereof which may include termination of its participation. The Terms of removal shall be fixed by a specific agreement under provisions set out in the section 7.2.2.

.4 SECTION: ENTRY INTO FORCE, DURATION AND TERMINATION

.4.1 ENTRY INTO FORCE

This Consortium Agreement shall come into force on the last date of signature by the (at least three) Parties, hereinafter referred to as the “Effective Date”.

.4.2 DURATION AND TERMINATION

This Consortium Agreement shall continue in full force and effect for a period of six (6) years after the Effective Date.

This Consortium Agreement may be extended or terminated before the expiration date by the Consortium Board by unanimous decision. Any and all extension of this Consortium Agreement shall be subject to the drafting of an amendment to be signed by the Parties.

.4.3 SURVIVAL OF RIGHTS AND OBLIGATIONS

The provisions relating to intellectual property rights, as well as for liability, applicable law and settlement of disputes shall survive for their own terms, notwithstanding the expiration or termination of this Consortium Agreement.

Termination shall not affect any rights or obligations of a Party leaving the Consortium incurred prior to the date of termination, unless otherwise agreed between the Consortium Board and the leaving Party.

.5 SECTION: RESPONSIBILITIES OF PARTIES

.5.1 GENERAL PRINCIPLES

Each Party makes its best efforts to efficiently execute its tasks as described in the Work Plan and to perform and fulfil, promptly and on time, all of its obligations.

Each Party shall promptly notify the Executive Board of any obstacles which may hinder the implementation of the Work Plan by that Party.

Each Party shall take reasonable measures to ensure the accuracy and correctness of any information it provides to the other Parties.

.6 SECTION: LIABILITY TOWARDS EACH OTHER

.6.1 NO WARRANTIES

In respect of any information or materials (incl. Results and Background) supplied by one Party to another in the context of this Consortium, no warranty or representation of any kind is made, given or implied as to the sufficiency or fitness for purpose nor as to the absence of any infringement of any proprietary rights of third parties.

Therefore,

- the recipient Party shall in all cases be entirely and solely liable for the use to which it puts such information and materials, and
- no Party granting access rights shall be liable in case of infringement of proprietary rights of a third party resulting from any other Party exercising its access rights.

.6.2 LIMITATIONS OF CONTRACTUAL LIABILITY

No Party shall be responsible to any other Party for any indirect or consequential loss or similar damage such as, but not limited to, loss of profit, loss of revenue or loss of contracts, provided such damage was not caused by a wilful act.

In any event, the maximum liability of any Party under or otherwise in connection with this Consortium Agreement or its subject matter shall not exceed €100,000.

.6.3 DAMAGE CAUSED TO THIRD PARTIES

A Party shall be solely liable for any loss, damage or injury to third parties resulting from the performance of the said Party's obligations by it or on its behalf under this Consortium Agreement or from its use of Results or Background.

.6.4 FORCE MAJEURE

No Party shall be considered to be in breach of this Consortium Agreement if it is prevented from fulfilling its obligations under the Consortium Agreement by Force Majeure.

Each Party will notify the competent Consortium Bodies of any Force Majeure without undue delay. If the consequences of Force Majeure for the Project are not overcome within 6 weeks after such notification, the transfer of tasks - if any - shall be decided by the competent Consortium Bodies.

.7 SECTION: GOVERNANCE STRUCTURE

.7.1 GENERAL STRUCTURE

The organisational structure of the Consortium shall comprise the following elements:

- Consortium Board as the ultimate decision-making body of the consortium - sect. 7.2,
- Executive Board as the supervisory body for the execution of the Work Plan, reporting and accountable to the Consortium Board - sect 7.3.
- Expert Advisory Committees consisting of (sect. 7.4):
 - User Feedback group
 - VA/TA Provider Committee
 - TA Selection Committee
- Think Tank consisting of (sect. 7.5):
 - Strategy and Scientific Board
 - Another community specific optional Group

Figure 1: Organisational structure of the Consortium

.7.2 OPERATIONAL PROCEDURES FOR THE CONSORTIUM BOARD

.7.2.1 Definition and composition

The Consortium Board shall consist of the representatives appointed by each Party.

Each Party has one (1) vote.

The Consortium Board will choose a chairperson with a term of three (3) years amongst its members, with a maximum of two (2) mandates. The chairperson shall not be from the institution which signs the Collaboration Agreement for TCS Governance and Coordination (see Sec 7.3).

In the Annex 1, each Party will indicate the name of its representative who will be authorised to deliberate, negotiate and decide on all matters listed in Section 7.2.2 of this Consortium Agreement. Every change to this list will be communicated to the chairperson of the Consortium Board. The chairperson of the Consortium Board will keep the list up to date and will communicate every change to all Parties.

In addition, the Consortium Board will include two (2) representatives from each EAC Advisory and Think Tank group for reporting and advice (without votes).

The chairperson shall chair all meetings of the Consortium Board, unless decided otherwise in a meeting of the Consortium Board.

.7.2.2 Tasks

The EPOS **XXX** Consortium Board is the principal and ultimate decision-making body of the EPOS **XXX** TCS. The Consortium Board shall be free to act on its own initiative to formulate proposals and take decisions in accordance with the procedures set out herein. In addition, all proposals made by the Executive Board shall also be considered and decided upon by the Consortium Board.

The following activities shall be undertaken by the Consortium Board.

- Discussion and approval of the Work Plan on an annual basis.
- Supervision of the proper execution of the actual Work Plan.
- Provide an overall leadership for the strategic direction to the consortium.
- High-level interactions with EPOS ERIC via Executive Board and Chairperson.
- Appointment of the members of the Executive Board, and, if necessary, extra-ordinary termination of their mandates.
- Appointment of Chairperson of the Consortium Board.
- Propose candidate(s) for TCS representative in Service Coordination Committee (SCC) to EPOS ERIC Executive Director.
- Identification and adaptation, when necessary, of mechanisms for quality check of service provision and compliance check of service provision.
- Review of the annual financial reporting and improvement.
- Recognition of the three (3) Expert Advisory Committees (EAC).
- Recognition of the Think Tank (Strategy and Scientific Board and **Another** Group).
- Handling disputes or conflicts.
- To declare a Party to be a defaulting Party and to decide on the consequences thereof which may include termination of its participation.
- Designation of institution(s) signing, on behalf of the Consortium, following Collaboration Agreements with EPOS ERIC:

- (i) for TCS Governance and Coordination (institution signing this Agreement automatically takes a role of the *TCS Coordinator* and its representative becomes Chairperson of the Executive Board);
- (ii) for TCS Data and Service Provision;
- (iii) for TCS Coordination of Transnational Access.

The three Collaboration Agreements mentioned above can be combined into one agreement with one signatory.

- Discussion and approval of every Collaboration Agreement.
- Controlling of the money flow between the signatories of the Collaboration Agreements and the respective DDSS providers, in accord with the Work Plan.

The following decisions shall be taken by the Consortium Board by unanimous vote:

- Entry of a new Party to the consortium and approval of the settlement on the conditions of the accession of such a new Party,
- Removal of a Party to the consortium and approval of the agreement on the conditions of the removal of this Party. The Party subject to this procedure is not entitled to take part in this vote.
- Approval of the agreement on the conditions of the withdrawal of a Party. The withdrawing Party is not entitled to take part in this vote.
- Extension or termination before the expiration date of the Consortium.

.7.2.3 Meetings

Any Party, which is a member of a Consortium Board:

- should be present or represented at any meeting,
- may appoint a substitute or a proxy to attend and vote at any meeting,
- shall participate in a cooperative manner in the meetings.

.7.2.4 Preparation and organisation of meetings

Ordinary meetings should take place at least once a year. In addition, at any time upon written request of the Executive Board or any member of the Consortium Board, extraordinary meetings may be called.

Chairperson of the Consortium Board shall give notice in writing of a meeting to each member of that Consortium Board as soon as possible and no later than the minimum number of days preceding the meeting as indicated below: 30 days for ordinary and 15 days for extraordinary meetings.

Any agenda item requiring a decision by the members of the Consortium Board must be identified as such on the agenda.

Any member of the Consortium Board may add an item to the original agenda by written notification to all members of the Consortium Board up to the minimum number of days preceding the meeting: 14 calendar days for ordinary and 7 calendar days for an extraordinary meeting.

During a meeting, members of the Consortium Board present or represented can unanimously agree to add a new item to the original agenda.

Meetings of the Consortium Board may be held by teleconference or other telecommunication means.

Decisions taken at Consortium Board meetings will only be binding once the relevant part of the Minutes has been accepted.

Any decision may also be adopted without a meeting. In this case, the Chairperson sends a written document to all members of the Consortium Board and asks for their approval within fifteen (15) calendar days. If a member has not answered (agreed or objected) in writing to the Chairperson within 15 calendar days, the decision shall be deemed adopted by this member. The decision shall be considered as accepted if

adopted by the specified majority of all members of the Consortium Board. After that, Chairperson sends the final notification to all members of the Consortium Board.

In the case of unanimous decisions, all voting members present or represented must agree.

.7.2.5 Voting rules, quorum and veto rights

A Party, which can show that its own work, time for performance, costs, liabilities, intellectual property rights or other legitimate interests would be severely affected by a decision of the Consortium Board, may exercise a veto with respect to the corresponding decision or relevant part of the decision. When the decision is foreseen on the original agenda, a member may veto such a decision during the meeting only.

When a decision has been made on a new item added to the agenda before or during the meeting, a member may veto such a decision during the meeting and within fifteen (15) calendar days after the draft minutes of the meeting are sent. When a decision has been taken without a meeting a member may veto such a decision within 15 calendar days after written notification by the chairperson of the outcome of the vote.

In case of exercise of veto, members of the Consortium Board shall make every effort to resolve the matter which occasioned the veto to the general satisfaction of all Parties.

A Party requesting to leave the Consortium or subject to an exclusion procedure may not veto decisions relating thereto.

The Consortium Board shall not deliberate and decide validly unless two-thirds (2/3) of its members who are entitled to vote are present or represented (quorum). If the quorum is not reached, the chairperson of the Consortium Board shall convene another ordinary meeting within 30 calendar days. If in this meeting the quorum is not reached once more, the chairperson shall convene an extraordinary meeting which shall be entitled to decide even if less than the quorum of members is present or represented.

Unless otherwise agreed at the beginning of a meeting, decisions shall be taken by a simple (1/2) majority of members entitled to vote that are present.

In the case of unanimous decisions, all voting members present or represented must agree.

.7.2.6 Minutes of meetings

Chairperson of the Consortium Board shall produce written Minutes of each meeting which shall be the formal record of all decisions taken. Draft Minutes should be sent to all the members within seven (7) calendar days of the meeting.

The Minutes shall be considered as accepted if, within fourteen (14) calendar days from sending, no member has sent an objection in writing to the Chairperson with respect to draft of the Minutes.

.7.3 OPERATIONAL PROCEDURES FOR THE EXECUTIVE BOARD

.7.3.1 Members

Members of the Executive Board are appointed by the Consortium Board for a period of three (3) years, with a maximum of two mandates. In addition, nominated representatives of the signatories of the Collaboration Agreements are members of the Executive Board by function and their period is determined by the duration of the Collaboration Agreement(s).

The Executive Board includes:

- Chairperson of the Consortium Board;
- Nominated representatives of the signatories of the Collaboration Agreements (1 per signatory institution);

- TCS representative in EPOS ERIC Service Coordination Committee (SCC) as appointed by EPOS ERIC Executive Director upon candidates proposed by the Consortium Board;
- One (1) representative of each of the service categories;
- TCS contact person (in EPOS ERIC) for service provision;
- TCS contact person for IT issues;
- TCS contact person for communication and outreach;
- TCS contact person for ethics issues;
- Secretary of the TCS (no vote, see 7.3.3).

Those members shall belong to at least five (5) different Parties.

The Chairperson of the Executive Board is a nominated representative of the TCS Coordinator (signatory of the Collaboration Agreement for TCS Governance and Coordination). The Chairperson of the Executive Board shall not be the same as the Chairperson of the Consortium Board. The Chairperson of the Executive Board may also be a TCS representative in EPOS Service Coordination Committee.

If needed the Executive Board can invite guests on specific questions, with no decision vote.

.7.3.2 Tasks

The Executive Board shall be responsible for the proper execution and implementation of the decisions of the Consortium Board. This includes the day-to-day coordination of TCS activities.

The Executive Board shall also monitor the effective and efficient implementation of the Work Plan, provide progress reports to the Consortium Board and propose modifications of the Work Plan to the Consortium Board on an annual basis.

The Executive Board is responsible for the day-to-day communication with EPOS ERIC.

The Executive Board is responsible for running the Expert Advisory Committees.

.7.3.3 Secretariat

The Executive Board shall be supported by a Secretariat. Funding can be generated by EPOS ERIC service support (service contract) or by contributions of the consortium members or by In-kind contributions. Decisions concerning utilisation of any funds are made by the Consortium Board. Tasks of the Secretariat will be support of the Executive Board in day-to-day coordination of the TCS, communication with other TCS and EPOS ERIC, preparation and organisations of TCS workshops, meetings of the Executive Board, meetings of the Consortium Board and meetings of the Advisory boards.

.7.3.4 Meetings

Ordinary meetings of the Executive Board should take place once in two (2) months. In addition, at any time upon the request of the Chairperson of the Executive Board, extraordinary meetings may be called.

.7.3.5 Voting rules and quorum

The Executive Board shall not deliberate and decide validly unless 2/3 of all of members who are entitled to vote are present or represented (quorum). If the quorum is not reached, the Chairperson shall convene another ordinary meeting within 15 calendar days. If in this meeting the quorum is not reached once more, the Chairperson shall convene an extraordinary meeting which shall be entitled to decide even if less than the quorum of Members is present or represented.

Each Member of the Executive Board present or represented in the meeting shall have one (1) vote. Unless otherwise agreed, decisions shall be taken by a two-third (2/3) majority.

.7.4 EXPERT ADVISORY COMMITTEES (EAC)

Three (3) Expert Advisory Committees (EAC's) will be set up:

- **The User Feedback Group:**
The User Feedback Group shall be composed of main representatives of the user community. Its members shall be appointed by the Consortium Board.
- **The VA/TA Provider Committee:**
VA and/or TA Provider Committee shall be composed of one representative of each of the Service and Data Suppliers listed in Annex 3.
- **The TA Selection Committee:**
The TA Selection Committee shall be composed of (external) experts in the relevant geoscience fields and representatives of TA providers. Its members shall be appointed by the Consortium Board.

Every EAC shall elect amongst its members, using a majority vote, two representatives to the Consortium Board. They will represent the EAC as non-voting members of the Consortium Board for advisory purposes. As a rule, these representatives have three (3)-year terms, which are renewable once.

Each EAC follows the progress of the Work Plan, advises the Consortium Board and provides recommendations to the chairperson of the Consortium Board.

The Consortium Board shall appoint amongst its members a person responsible for convening the EAC's at least once a year, attending the EAC meetings, safeguarding the minutes of the EAC meetings and preparing the recommendations of the EAC's for the Consortium Board.

.7.5 THINK TANK

The Think Tank consists of **two (2)** Internal Expert Advisory Committees:

- **The Strategy and Scientific Board**
The TCS has a Strategy and Scientific Board (SSB) which consists of Consortium members and will discuss the community strategy for the development of new and advanced services or standards for data and products or any other issues if relevant. Membership is discussed and defined by the Consortium Board for (3) years. The Strategy and Scientific Board discussions are open to every Consortium member, and may invite external experts.
- **Another community specific optional Group**
Description of the Another think-tank Group...

Each Think Tank group elects a chairperson among its members by majority vote for three (3) years, with a maximum of two (2) mandates.

Every Think Tank group shall elect amongst its members, using a majority vote, two representatives to the Consortium Board. They will represent the group of the Think Tank as non-voting members of the Consortium Board for advisory purposes. As a rule, these representatives have three (3)-year terms, which are renewable once.

Each Think Tank group follows the progress of the Work Plan, advises the Consortium Board and provides recommendations to the chairperson of the Consortium Board.

.8 SECTION: SERVICE PROVISION UNDER THE EPOS DELIVERY FRAMEWORK

One mission of the Thematic Core Service **XXX** is provision, through the EPOS Delivery Framework, of access to **XXX**-related digital assets and experimental facilities.

Virtual Access (VA) to digital assets (datasets, observations, software) will be provided, depending on the assets type, either through the official EPOS Integrated Core Services (ICS-C) Data Portal <https://www.ics-c.epos-eu.org/> (for example, geo-referenced datasets which are or could be made compatible with the OGC data standards), or linked through the TCS **XXX** Community Portal [link to the portal](#) (for example, software repositories or observation streaming services).

Trans-national Access (TA) to experimental facilities or selected HPC-workflows will be conveyed directly through the participating Partners.

In case new VA is or can be made compatible to the EPOS Data Portal, EPOS ICS-TCS Interaction Team will assist service integration into the Portal through short-term projects called pitches (e.g., publishing of a database at a Geoserver, co-definition of metadata compatible to the EPOS DCAT-AP metadata catalogue, etc.).

.9 SECTION: FINANCIAL PROVISIONS FOR TCS SERVICES

Each Party shall rely on its own resources by participation in general activities of the TCS **XXX**.

All services (DDSS elements) provided to EPOS ERIC shall be described in Collaboration Agreements together with their financial aspects. Budget aspects of each service provision shall be additionally defined in the TCS Cost-Book.

.10 SECTION: DATA, INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS, RESULTS

.10.1 GENERAL PRINCIPLES

The general principles and process of handling data and intellectual property rights within the activities of the EPOS research Infrastructure are laid down in the EPOS Data Policy (Annex 2). This data policy will also apply on all activities of this Consortium.

.10.2 OWNERSHIP OF RESULT

.10.2.1 Management of results

Results obtained in the framework of this agreement shall belong to the Party or Parties generating them. In case of Results generated by several Parties, hereafter referred as “Joint Owners”, the co-ownership rate and intellectual property costs will be equally shared between the said Parties.

Parties undertake to sign in good faith any legal instrument enabling them to exercise proprietary rights over the Results in accordance with this agreement prior any exploitation. It is agreed that the Parties shall proceed in the interest of the inventors, in accordance with the legislation.

.10.2.2 Software

In addition to the provisions set out in Sections 10.1 and 10.2.1, the Core Software shall remain the property of the Party which holds it prior to the signing of the Consortium Agreement.

Adaptations carried out, regardless of the author, in the framework of the Consortium Agreement, shall be the property of the Party owning the Core Software. Accordingly, where the Party having carried out Adaptations is not the owner of the Core Software, it undertakes to assign the right of use of such Adaptations, free of charge, to the Party owning the Core Software, including the right to reproduce, represent, translate, adapt, arrange, alter and market the Adaptation.

Each Party shall be the owner of the Extension produced by it within the framework of the Consortium Agreement, regardless of which Party is the owner of the Core Software from which such Extensions are derived.

Extensions produced jointly by the Parties, regardless of which party is the initial owner of the Core Software from which such extensions are derived, shall be the joint property of the Parties.

The Shared Software shall be the jointly owned property of the Parties.

.10.2.3 Use of results

Each Party is hereby granted an irrevocable, non-transferable, royalty-free right to use Results obtained in the framework of this agreement for academic and research purposes, including research involving projects funded by third parties provided that those parties gain or claim no rights to such Results.

Prior to any industrial and commercial use of the jointly owned Results by a Joint Owner or third party, the Joint Owners shall specify the terms and conditions to exploit the jointly owned Results or to grant (exclusive or non-exclusive) licenses to third parties in a joint ownership agreement or an exploitation agreement to third party.

As of now, the Parties agree that any direct and/or indirect use of the jointly owned Results by a Joint Owner or third Party shall be subject to fair and reasonable financial compensation being paid to the other Joint Owners according to terms and conditions set forth subsequently in the abovementioned joint ownership and or exploitation agreements.

.10.3 DISSEMINATION

For the avoidance of doubt, nothing in this Section has an impact on the confidentiality obligations set out in Section 10.

.10.3.1 Dissemination of another Party's unpublished Results or Background

A Party shall not include in any dissemination activity another Party's Results or Background without obtaining the owning Party's prior written approval, unless they are already published or disseminated and the licensing of the specific item allows for it.

The Parties reserve the right to publish and/or present, entirely or in part, Results of the activities that are the subject of the present Agreement, provided confidential delivery of a draft of the publication and/or presentation is made to the owning Party at least 30 (thirty) days prior to delivery thereof to third parties.

The owning Party may:

- a. no later than 20 (twenty) days from receipt of the draft, notify the Party in writing as to which confidential information must not be revealed to third parties; or
- b. no later than 20 (twenty) days from receipt of the draft, request in writing that the publication and/or presentation is postponed for a period not exceeding 90 (ninety) days in order to allow for the filing of an application for intellectual property rights where the owning Party has a right thereto in terms of this Agreement or applicable laws.

In the event that the owning Party fails to reply as above indicated, the requesting Party may, without further notice, freely send a draft of the publication and/or the presentation to third parties. The

requesting Party undertakes to state, within its publications or presentations, that the results were achieved during the course of the relationship that is the subject of the present Agreement.

.10.3.2 Cooperation obligations

The Parties undertake to cooperate to allow the timely submission, examination, publication and defence of any dissertation or thesis for a degree that includes their Results or Background subject to the confidentiality and publication provisions agreed in this Consortium Agreement.

.10.3.3 Use of names, logos or trademarks

Nothing in this Consortium Agreement shall be construed as conferring rights to use in advertising, publicity or otherwise the name of the Parties or any of their logos or trademarks without their prior written approval.

.11 SECTION: NON-DISCLOSURE OF INFORMATION

All information in whatever form or mode of communication, which is disclosed by a Party (the “Disclosing Party”) to another Party (the “Recipient”), in connection with the Work Plan and which has been explicitly marked as “confidential” at the time of disclosure, or when disclosed orally has been identified as confidential at the time of disclosure and has been confirmed and designated in writing within thirty (30) calendar days from oral disclosure at the latest as confidential information by the Disclosing Party, is “Confidential Information”.

The Recipients hereby undertake for a period of three (3) years after the Disclosing:

- not to use Confidential Information otherwise than for the purpose for which it was disclosed,
- not to disclose Confidential Information to any other recipients including affiliated third parties without the prior written consent by the Disclosing Party,
- to ensure that internal distribution of Confidential Information by a Recipient shall take place on a strict need-to-know basis,
- to return to the Disclosing Party, or destroy, on request all Confidential Information that has been disclosed to the Recipients including all copies thereof and to delete all information stored in a machine readable form to the extent practically possible. The Recipients may keep a copy to the extent it is required to keep, archive or store such Confidential Information because of compliance with applicable laws and regulations or for the proof of on-going obligations provided that the Recipient comply with the confidentiality obligations herein contained with respect to such copy for as long as the copy is retained.

The Recipients shall be responsible for the fulfilment of the above obligations on the part of their employees and shall ensure that they remain so obliged, as far as legally possible, during the Consortium and/or after the termination of the contractual relationship with the employee.

The above shall not apply for disclosure or use of Confidential Information, if and in so far as the Recipient can show that:

- the Confidential Information has become or becomes publicly available by means other than a breach of the Recipient’s confidentiality obligations;
- the Disclosing Party subsequently informs the Recipient that the Confidential Information is no longer confidential;
- the Confidential Information, at any time, was developed by the Recipient completely independently of any such disclosure by the Disclosing Party;

- the Confidential Information was already known to the Recipient prior to disclosure, or
- the Recipient is required to disclose the Confidential Information in order to comply with applicable laws or regulations or with a court or administrative order, subject to the provision Section 10 last paragraph hereunder.

The Recipient shall apply the same degree of care with regard to the Confidential Information disclosed within the scope of the Consortium as with its own confidential and/or proprietary information, but in no case less than reasonable care

Each Party shall promptly advise the other Party in writing of any unauthorised disclosure, misappropriation or misuse of Confidential Information after it becomes aware of such unauthorised disclosure, misappropriation or misuse.

If any Party becomes aware that it will be required, or is likely to be required, to disclose Confidential Information in order to comply with applicable laws or regulations or with a court or administrative order, it shall, to the extent it is lawfully able to do so, prior to any such disclosure:

- notify the Disclosing Party,
- comply with the Disclosing Party's reasonable instructions to protect the confidentiality of the information.

.12 SECTION: MISCELLANEOUS

.12.1 ANNEXES, INCONSISTENCIES AND SEVERABILITY

This Consortium Agreement consists of this core text and:

- Annex 1: Representative of each party who will be authorised to deliberate, negotiate and decide on all matters listed in Section 7.2.2
- Annex 2: EPOS data policy
- Annex 3: List of proposed services and service providers

In case of conflicts between the Annexes and the core text of this Consortium Agreement, the latter shall prevail. Any and all modifications to the Articles of this Consortium Agreement shall be subject to the drafting of an amendment to be signed by the Parties. Modifications to Annexes 1 and 2 are automatically accepted and updated at least on a yearly basis by the Executive Board. Modifications to Annex 3 should be approved by the Consortium Board.

Should any provision of this Consortium Agreement become invalid, illegal or unenforceable, it shall not affect the validity of the remaining provisions of this Consortium Agreement. In such a case, the Parties concerned shall be entitled to request that a valid and practicable provision be negotiated that fulfils the purpose of the original provision.

.12.2 NO REPRESENTATION, PARTNERSHIP OR AGENCY

Except as otherwise provided in Section 7, no Party shall be entitled to act or to make legally binding declarations on behalf of any other Party or of the Consortium Agreement. Nothing in this Consortium Agreement shall be deemed to constitute a joint venture, agency, partnership, interest grouping or any other kind of formal business grouping or entity between the Parties.

.12.3 NOTICES AND OTHER COMMUNICATION

Any notice to be given under this Consortium Agreement shall be in writing to the addresses and recipients as listed in the most current address list kept by the chairperson of the Consortium Board.

.12.3.1 Formal notices

If it is required in this Consortium Agreement that a formal notice, consent or approval shall be given, such notice shall be signed by an authorised representative of a Party and shall either be served personally or sent by e-mail with acknowledgement of receipt, which fulfils the conditions of written form.

.12.3.2 Other communication

Other communication between the Parties may also be effected by other means such as e-mail with acknowledgement of receipt, which fulfils the conditions of written form.

.12.3.3 Change of persons or contact details

Any change of persons or contact details shall be notified immediately by the respective Party to the chairperson of the Consortium Board. The address list shall be accessible to all Parties.

.12.4 MANDATORY NATIONAL LAW

Nothing in this Consortium Agreement shall be deemed to require a Party to breach any mandatory statutory law under which the Party is operating.

.12.5 LANGUAGE

This Consortium Agreement is drawn up in English, which language shall govern all documents, notices, meetings, arbitral proceedings and processes relative thereto.

.12.6 APPLICABLE LAW

This Consortium Agreement shall be construed in accordance with and governed by the laws of Belgium excluding its conflict of law provisions.

.12.7 SETTLEMENT OF DISPUTES

The parties shall endeavour to settle their disputes amicably.

Any dispute, controversy or claim arising under, out of or relating to this Consortium Agreement and any subsequent amendments of this contract, including, without limitation, its formation, validity, binding effect, interpretation, performance, breach or termination, as well as non-contractual claims, shall be submitted to the Belgian courts.

Nothing in this Consortium Agreement shall limit the Parties' right to seek injunctive relief in any applicable competent court.

– END OF THE MAIN TEXT –

SIGNATURES:

Partner 1 Name (Abbreviation)

Address

Signature _____

Date of signature: _____

Name of the signing person:

Position in the organization:

Signature _____

Date of signature: _____

Name of the signing person:

Position in the organization:

ANNEX 1: REPRESENTATIVE OF EACH PARTY AT THE CONSORTIUM BOARD

<List of representatives authorised to deliberate, negotiate and decide on all matters listed in Section 7.2.2. Up to date version of this list will be maintained by the Chairperson of the Consortium Board>

- 1.
- 2.
- 3.

ANNEX 2: EPOS DATA POLICY

Available from the EPOS website, “Documents” section: <https://www.epos-eu.org/epos-eric/documents>.

ANNEX 3: LIST OF PROPOSED SERVICES AND SERVICE PROVIDERS

Category	Service	Description	Provided by

